
Rounded up: Using round numbers to identify tax evasion

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Key findings

Taxpayers display a preference for round-number tax refunds, and bunching at these numbers is:

- Driven by tax evasion (including errors) rather than effort.
- Driven by tax return items that are costly to audit (such as work-related expense deductions).
- More common in agent-prepared returns.

What we knew

- Taxpayers act in ways to avoid owing a debt to the tax authority when filing their tax return (see Rees-Jones (2018) for the USA; Engström, Nordblom, Ohlsson and Persson (2015) for Sweden).
- This is consistent with classic models of loss aversion, where people place a premium on reducing or avoiding a ‘loss’.
- In this paper we look beyond this to consider:
 - whether taxpayers have preferences with respect to other aspects of their tax refund;
 - how taxpayers and tax agents respond to such preferences; and
 - what these responses tell us about the tax system.

What we do

- We use de-identified tax return data from 1991 to 2018 (ALife) (Abhayaratna, Carter and Johnson (2022)) to follow individuals and their tax agents over time.
- We examine the distribution of the ‘balance of assessment’ — how much people owe or are owed by the ATO after filing their tax return.
- We explore how bunching in this distribution is consistent with preferences for ‘round numbers’ and what this behaviour can tell us about taxpayers, tax agents and the tax system.
- We draw on random audit data to determine if this bunching is driven by ‘effort’ or ‘evasion’.

What we know now

- Australian taxpayers bunch at thousand-, hundred- and ten-dollar thresholds (Figure 1). They are much more likely to get \$1,000 back from the ATO than \$999.
- Random audit data suggests this bunching is driven by evasion rather than effort. To reach these round numbers, taxpayers and their agents are making claims that don’t survive audit.
- Bunching at round numbers:
 - Is more common in electronic returns.

Figure 1: Distribution of balance of assessment, 1991-2018

Note: Distribution of the balance of assessment for those with: strictly positive net tax liability and tax withheld; and a balance of assessment consistent with the remainder of the tax return. Counts are for each \$A1 bin, with diamonds indicating counts at positive hundred-dollar thresholds. For visual clarity we exclude the count at zero balance of assessment, which is 22,870. Sample consists of 22.5 million tax returns over the 1991-2018 income years.

- Is associated with greater loyalty to the tax agents that facilitate it.
- Has become more prevalent over time (reflecting the dynamics described above).
- Bunching is about twice as common in agent-prepared returns, though tax agents differ in their propensity to deliver such returns. Some bunch a lot and others not at all.
- When taxpayers move to a ‘high bunching’ agent, they experience a step change in income and deductions that are costly to audit, with especially significant increases in work-related expense deductions. But these deductions do not grow over time, as we would expect if these agents were helping taxpayers to plan for the future (e.g. by keeping receipts, or more readily incurring claimable expenses).

What this means for policy

- This evidence shines a light on tax evasion and serves as a useful complement to random audits.
- Tax authorities might benefit from factoring bunching behaviours into existing risk models — though such models are rightly not made public.
- Our findings point to considerable ‘discretion’ when taxpayers file their return, reflecting complexity in the system. This complexity undermines equity and efficiency.
- A simpler system that more clearly reflects economic choices and outcomes in the tax year, over post hoc decisions about what kind of refund to target, would be preferable. Work-related expense deductions reform is one route to a simpler tax system, as discussed in the Henry tax review, *The Commonwealth of Australia* (2010).

Where to now?

- Further work would clarify the different roles and behaviours of tax agents in the tax system.
- While deductions have been subject to significant study by tax economists, the study of aspects such as the extent to which deductions reflect personal consumption is still in its infancy. Such studies merit consideration for policy.

More information

- Get the full paper at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0047272724001312>.
- We would welcome the opportunity to present our research to your team and to discuss potential joint research projects on related or similar topics.
- Contact us at robert.breunig@anu.edu.au

References

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